

اسلام میں فوز و فلاح کا تصور

THE CONCEPT OF FAUZ-O-FALAH IN ISLAM

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ABSTRACT

The concept of "Fauz o Falah" in Islam represents the twin ideals of success and prosperity that are sought by Muslims in both worldly matters and their spiritual journey. "Fauz" refers to achieving success and victory, not only in the material sense but also in overcoming trials and challenges that one may encounter. It signifies triumph in various aspects of life, such as personal endeavors, community welfare, and societal progress.

On the other hand, "Falah" denotes attaining prosperity and salvation, primarily in the spiritual context. It encompasses a sense of spiritual well-being, righteousness, and closeness to Allah. Muslims believe that true prosperity lies in leading a righteous life, following the teachings of Islam, and seeking forgiveness for sins.

The concept of Fauz o Falah is deeply rooted in Islamic teachings and is often used to encourage Muslims to strive for excellence, not only in the pursuit of worldly success but also in strengthening their faith and connection with Allah. It reminds believers to seek both material achievements and spiritual enlightenment, recognizing that true fulfillment comes from striking a balance between the two realms. By seeking success and prosperity while adhering to moral and ethical principles, Muslims aim to attain a state of contentment and eternal bliss in this life and the hereafter.

Keywords: Authentic fulfillment, Bliss, Worldly, Real Success, Heaven, Hell.

کلیدی الفاظ: فوز، فلاح، دنیاوی، حقیقی کامیابی، خسارہ، جنت، دوزخ۔

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